

DISPERSION BEHAVIOR OF MODES IN PARTIALLY OPEN
MICROSTRIP ON A SEMICONDUCTOR LAYERED SUBSTRATE

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Introduction: Slow wave electromagnetic structures compatible with hybrid circuit or monolithic processing are of interest at millimeter wave frequencies. Here a dielectric (or space charge depleted)-semiconductor substrate structure with a microstrip line above it is studied. Similar structures have been examined at frequencies mostly below 10 GHz for only the fundamental mode [1,2]. Here focus is placed on obtaining the complex propagation constant γ in the 10-140 GHz range for many modes.

Theory: The partially open microstrip structure has electric walls placed at $x=\pm a$ (Fig. 1). These walls allow the use of a discrete Fourier transform method enabling the current distribution on the microstrip line ($|x|\leq w/2$) and the fields to be constructed from an infinite sum for the x dependence. Summation is preferable to an integral Fourier transform technique on an infinite space with oscillatory integrands requiring numerical evaluation. A superposition of the TM_z and TE_z fields using a vector potential construction must be used to satisfy the boundary conditions (B.C.) at the $y=b_1$ interface. This hybrid mode approach is covered below [3], [4]. Satisfaction of the tangential B.C.'s on E_x and E_z on the $x=\pm a$ walls is required noting that $E_z(x,y) \propto \psi_z(x,y)$, and employing an acceptable Fourier series representation. A complete orthogonal set of exponential functions capable of representing any function $f(x)$, such as $\psi_z^{(j)}(x,y)$ on $(-a,a)$ where $j = e(TM_z)$ or $m(TE_z)$, enables the use of the following Fourier series construction and associated transform (tilde denotes Fourier):

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{2a} \sum_{p=-\infty}^{\infty} \tilde{f}(p) e^{-jk_p x} = \frac{1}{a} \sum_{p=1}^{\infty} \tilde{f}(p) \begin{Bmatrix} \cos(k_p x) \\ -j \sin(k_p x) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$\tilde{f}(p) = \int_{-a}^a f(x) e^{jk_p x} dx \quad (2)$$

In the second equality of (1), the $\cos(k_p x)$ factor is used if $f(x) =$ even in x , and $\sin(k_p x)$ used if $f(x) =$ odd in x . The field solution for the microstrip problem is decomposed into two parts, the solution giving $E_z(x,y)$ with even x symmetry and the solution giving E_z with odd x symmetry. Even and odd solutions are obtained by respectively setting $k_p = (p-\frac{1}{2})\pi/a$, $p\pi/a$.

Surface currents exist only on the microstrip line ($|x|\leq w/2$), $J_x(x,y=b_1) = J_x(x)$ and $J_z(x,y=b_1) = J_z(x)$. They can be constructed from an infinite set of basis functions (Galerkin's method) which are not necessarily orthogonal.

$$J_x(x) = \sum_{m=1}^M c_m J_{xm}(x) \quad ; \quad J_z(x) = \sum_{m=1}^N d_m J_{zm}(x) \quad (3a,b)$$

Finite summation limits M and N in (3) indicate truncation after a limited number of terms. Other B.C.'s to be satisfied are $E_{x3} = E_{z3} = 0$ ($y=b_2$), $E_{x3} = H_{x2}$, $H_{x3} = H_{x2}$, $E_{z3} = E_{z2}$, and $H_{z3} = H_{z2}$ ($y=0$), and $|x|\leq w/2$

$$H_{x1}(x,b_1) - H_{x2}(x,b_1) = J_x(x) \quad , \quad H_{z2}(x,b_1) - H_{z1}(x,b_1) = J_z(x) \quad (4a,b)$$

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$\tilde{E}_{z1}$ and $\tilde{H}_{z1}$ at $y=b_1$ are found by applying all the B.C.s in the Fourier transformed domain, using the separation equation

$$-k_p^2 + \gamma_i^2 + k_i^2 + \gamma^2 = 0 \quad (5)$$

In (5) γ_i are the y-direction complex propagation constants used in the formulation of the magnetic $\psi_i^{(e)}$ or electric $\psi_i^{(h)}$ potentials of the i th region in terms of hyperbolic functions (except in region 1 where they are of the form $e^{-\gamma_1 y}$). Defining $Q(p, \gamma) = \tanh(\gamma_2 b_1) / (\bar{h}_1 \bar{g}_2' - \bar{h}_2 \bar{g}_1')$,

$$\tilde{E}_{z1}(p, b_1, z) = \frac{\gamma^2 + k_1^2}{j\omega\mu_1'} Q(p, \gamma) [\bar{h}_1 \tilde{J}_x(p) + \bar{h}_2 \tilde{J}_z(p)] e^{-\gamma z} \quad (6)$$

$$\tilde{H}_{z1}(p, b_1, z) = -\frac{\gamma^2 + k_1^2}{j\omega\mu_1'} Q(p, \gamma) [\bar{g}_1' \tilde{J}_x(p) + \bar{g}_2' \tilde{J}_z(p)] e^{-\gamma z} \quad (7)$$

Two remaining B.C.'s must be applied at the $y=b_1$ interface:

$$E_{z1}(x, b_1) = \frac{\gamma^2 + k_1^2}{j\omega\epsilon_1'} u(x) \quad ; \quad \frac{dH_{z1}(x, b_1)}{dy} = \frac{\gamma^2 + k_1^2}{j\omega\mu_1'} v(x) \quad (8)$$

Here $u(x)=v(x)=0$ when $|x| \leq w/2$. Fourier transforming (8) and equating to (6) and (7) yields

$$G_{11}(p, \gamma) \tilde{J}_x(p) + G_{12}(p, \gamma) \tilde{J}_z(p) = \tilde{u}(p) \quad (9)$$

$$G_{21}(p, \gamma) \tilde{J}_x(p) + G_{22}(p, \gamma) \tilde{J}_z(p) = \tilde{v}(p) \quad (10)$$

where

$$G_{11}(p, \gamma) = \bar{h}_1(p, \gamma) Q(p, \gamma) \quad ; \quad G_{12}(p, \gamma) = \bar{h}_2(p, \gamma) Q(p, \gamma) \quad (11a, b)$$

$$G_{21}(p, \gamma) = \gamma_1 \bar{g}_1'(p, \gamma) Q(p, \gamma) \quad ; \quad G_{22}(p, \gamma) = \gamma_1 \bar{g}_2'(p, \gamma) Q(p, \gamma) \quad (11c, d)$$

Equations (9) and (10) containing γ can be converted into a single dispersion equation as follows. Substitution of the Fourier transforms of (3) into (9) and (10) generates two equations, each with $M+N$ unknown amplitudes c_m and d_m on the left hand sides (LHS). Multiplying (9) then by $J_{xi}(p)$ ($i=1, 2, \dots, N$) and (10) by $J_{xi}(p)$ ($i=1, 2, \dots, M$) allows the creation of $\sum_{i=1}^{M+N} M+N$ equations in $M+N$ unknown amplitudes. Applying the inverse Fourier transform $\sum_{p=1}^{\infty}$ to these equations gives

$$\sum_{m=1}^M A_{im}^{11}(\gamma) c_m + \sum_{m=1}^N A_{im}^{12}(\gamma) d_m = \sum_{p=1}^{\infty} \tilde{J}_{zi}(p) \tilde{u}(p); \quad i=1, 2, \dots, N \quad (12a)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^M A_{im}^{21}(\gamma) c_m + \sum_{m=1}^N A_{im}^{22}(\gamma) d_m = \sum_{p=1}^{\infty} \tilde{J}_{x1}(p) \tilde{v}(p); \quad i=1, 2, \dots, M \quad (12b)$$

$$A_{im}^{st}(\gamma) = \int_{p=1}^{\infty} \tilde{J}_{s,i}(p) G_{st}(p, \gamma) \tilde{J}_{t,m}(p); \quad s', t' = x, z \text{ if } s=2, 1 \text{ or } t=1, 2 \quad (13)$$

$A_{im}^{st}(\gamma)$ ($s, t=1, 2$) are calculated exactly by setting $L=\infty$ in (13). The right-hand-sides of (12) are easily seen to be zero due to the spatial complementary nature of $E_{z1}(x, b_1)$, and $J_{zi}(x, b_1)$ and $J_{xi}(x, b_1)$. Equations (12), linear homogeneous equations with coefficients A_{im}^{st} , are solved by setting the determinant of the LHS of the $M+N$ equations to zero. This procedure gives a single dispersion equation in γ , with no necessity for

knowing c_m or d_m . It is desirable to choose current basis functions carefully so that they are physically plausible since this information is embedded in the dispersion equation. As M and $N \rightarrow \infty$, however, this need is relaxed considerably, at the expense of greatly increased complexity and computer computation time. The approach here uses $M=N=1$, giving the dispersion relationship

$$A_{11}^{11}(\gamma) A_{11}^{22}(\gamma) - A_{11}^{12}(\gamma) A_{11}^{21}(\gamma) = 0 \quad (14)$$

All field components if wanted (all regions) can be found from the vector potential formulation once γ is determined from (14).

Numerical Results: Microstrip parameters are set to $\epsilon_{r1}=4.5$, $\epsilon_{r2}=12$, $b_1=0.3 \mu\text{m}$, $b_2=190 \mu\text{m}$, $a=5000 \mu\text{m}$, $w=1000 \mu\text{m}$, and $\sigma=10^{-3} \text{U/m}$ (medium β) for the $\sigma > 0$ case. For $\sigma < 0$, $\epsilon_{r1}=\epsilon_{r2}=12$, $b_1=0.3 \mu\text{m}$, $b_2=200 \mu\text{m}$, $a=5000 \mu\text{m}$, $w=1000 \mu\text{m}$, and $\sigma=10^{-3} \text{U/m}$. Because the dispersion results are not overly sensitive to the particular choice of current basis functions, and to maintain simplicity, $J_z(x)$ and $J_z(x)$ are constructed through (3) using one basis function apiece. These basis functions are $J_{z1}(x)=1/w$, $J_{z2}(x)=(-j/\pi w)\sin(2\pi x/w)$ for even modes and $J_{z1}(x)=-2jx/w^2$, $J_{z2}(x)=(2/\pi w)\cos(\pi x/w)$ for odd modes when $x \leq w/2$ and zero otherwise. L in (13) is set to 30 terms (except for branch B1 where $L=100$) in Fig. 2 and 100 in Fig. 3 for respectively the even and odd modes. Beyond about $L=30$ the even mode results are relatively insensitive to additional terms (the effect is on the order of 1% or less) whereas for the odd modes this insensitivity begins at larger L so $L=100$ is chosen.

For $\sigma > 0$ and low frequencies $f < 20$ GHz decreasing β of the branches B1, B2, ... corresponds to increasing α (as in Figs. 2 and 3) but this progression is disrupted at higher frequencies, for example at 70 GHz. The progression is reversed beyond 90 GHz for the branches B1-B5, but this trend is not necessarily true for the other higher order modes not plotted in the figures. What appears to be occurring is that at high frequencies, say 90 GHz, the B1 branch wave is being guided significantly by the (open air space)-layers combination. A surface wave is brought into existence which samples appreciably the air environment with some of the electromagnetic field energy lying above the $y=b_1$ interface. The effect is not as large for the B2 branch wave relative to the B1 branch wave at 90 GHz, therefore its $\beta_2 > \beta_1$. Such an argument explains the results in Figs. 2 and 3. The even and odd mode results differ much more in β than α , the α differences being small. β differences can be as large as 25% if branch peaks are compared. Even mode $\sigma < 0$ results are given in Fig. 4 using $L=100$ terms. The behavior of γ for $\sigma < 0$ is very similar to the $\sigma > 0$ results. Comparison of the $\sigma < 0$ (Fig. 4) and $\sigma > 0$ (Fig. 2) results makes clear that the β curves for $\sigma < 0$ are much closer and more sharply peaked when examining the branches B_i , $i \geq 2$. The peaks, for corresponding β branch curves of the $\sigma > 0$ and $\sigma < 0$ results, are much larger for the $\sigma < 0$ case, differing by as much as 2.8:1.

References

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Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4